

Scrawlink: Live sharing of live coding scores using QR codes

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ABSTRACT

Live coding is a performance technique using programming languages to produce sounds and visuals, among others. Typically, the code is programmed live. Sharing this code is often encouraged, and it is considered a key element of live coding performances. However, this often happens only through the sharing of the performer's screen. Using, studying, sharing, and improving these programs (the four free software freedoms) is therefore a challenge, as access to the code is lost after it changes or the performance finishes.

This paper introduces Scrawlink, a software that enables sharing the performance's code in working live coding environments using QR codes. The proposal aims to provide affordable and culturally appropriate ways to store, share, and reproduce live coding "scores" to support the open values of the community, and enable new ways of collaboration, composition and inclusion.

Scrawlink supports different web-based languages, such as Strudel (audio), Hydra (visuals), or WebPD (web Pure Data instruments). It is performance oriented, as the scores are automatically shared as the performer changes the code, and supports directly playing the scores in working live coding environments. The tool facilitates live sharing of live coding scores, a practice that could be a key to transform live coding, facilitating code sharing, collaboration and publishing practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Live coding uses programming to perform live music and visuals among others (Collins et al. 2003). The code producing the sounds and visuals is changed live, and it is typically shared with the audiences, projecting the screens of the performers, as expressed by the commonly used "show us your screens" principle¹. Toplap manifesto demands that "Code should be seen as well as heard, underlying algorithms viewed as well as their visual outcome." Thus, sharing the code of the performances is a core aspect of the live coding culture and ethics.

The sharing of the code happens mainly sharing the screens at the live performances, and it is difficult to access it after the show finishes. Sometimes the code could also be accessed through the recordings of the performances. However, copying the code from videos is not straightforward, and sometimes is not even possible if the code is not clearly visible. Thus, despite the desired openness, accessing the live coding source codes is not always easy.

This paper introduces Scrawlink, a software that enables live sharing of live coding performances code in working web-based live coding environments. It uses QR codes that change when the performance code changes to give access to the code (score) and environment (instrument) to the

¹ Toplap Manifesto Draft: <http://toplap.org/wiki/ManifestoDraft>

audience. Thus, the proposal aims to support the sharing of live coding “scores”, to enable easier ways to store, share and reproduce live coding pieces and performances, and aims to foster the open values of the community, enabling new ways of collaboration, composition and inclusion.

The following sections provide the background of the proposal (Section 2), an overview of the design (Section 3), a description of the implementation and architecture (Section 4), and the evaluation of the proposal at different scenarios (Section 5). Finally, Section 6 discusses the results and concludes the paper.

2. BACKGROUND

The open sharing of source code in live coding is linked to the sharing values of the Free Software and the Open Source communities. Moreover, the sharing of music scores have a long tradition that continues in contemporary practices. This section provides situates the proposal in these traditions of software and music scores sharing.

Live coding culture and the four Free Software freedoms

Live coding is strongly connected to the free software culture and hacker ethics (Kirkpatrick 2002; Ledesma 2015), as it promotes free sharing of the code and processes. This can be seen in Toplap manifesto Draft² “show us your screens”, “Code should be seen as well as heard, underlying algorithms viewed as well as their visual outcome.” or in Algorave guidelines³ “Exposing algorithmic processes”.

Sharing practices beyond projecting the screens during performances, include videos and photos of the performances, collaborative sessions using environments such as Estuary (Ogborn et al. 2017) and Flock⁴, workshops and community events such as “from scratch” sessions, sharing code snippets through internet channels such as discord or telegram channels, or SuperCollider tweets (Martins and Padovani 2023). Moreover, some of the web live coding environments such as Hydra, Strudel or P5Live support link sharing to the code and environment, and some live coders have even published complete songs using this functionality⁵.

Despite the existence of these different live coding sharing practices, most performances’ code is not shared beyond the projection of the screens. Thus, it is often a challenge to access it. This seems to be in conflict with the open principles of the community. However, not sharing the code might also support the improvisational and ephemeral nature of algoraves. This immediacy and lack of recordings are even explicitly supported principles, such as in the Toplap manifesto: “No backup” preference or “Why repeat the past”. This extreme is recognized by the practitioners “*We do not study each other's pieces*” (Sonic Writing 2016) as quoted in (Dal Rì and Masu 2022).

However, sharing code in a way that is easy to play and modify could also support other explicit values of the community⁶, such as accessibility and diversity (J. Armitage and Thornham 2021).

Live coding & Scores

Live coding has a highly improvisatory element, the performances are far from “fixed” works of art that traditionally use scores (Zeilinger 2014). However, scores serve many purposes in

² Available online at <https://toplap.org/wiki/ManifestoDraft>

³ Available online at https://github.com/Algorave/guidelines/blob/master/README_en.md

⁴ Available online: <https://next.flok.cc>

⁵ Array (Lil Data Edit) by DJ_Dave https://strudel.cc/?mTeJt_ICoPw

⁶ See for instance *Algorave* or *CLiC: Colectivo de Live coders* community guidelines .

contemporary musical practices, and their relevance for live coding has been highlighted as interfaces “where the code (a form of notation) is the input of the digital system that is created or manipulated during a performance” (Dal Rì and Masu 2022). Moreover, some live coding interfaces even provide a graphical, and not only textual, representation of the code (Magnusson 2011).

3. DESIGN

Scrawlink aims to provide easy ways to share live coding scores. It was introduced in a workshop called “Live coding para todes” (live coding for all⁷ in Spanish) at *Sync! Festival*⁸ with the explicit goal of supporting diverse live coding scenes and targeted to “bodies often excluded from electronic music and programming”. Thus, its design not only aimed to support the sharing of live coding scores, but doing it in a way that supported easy ways to play, modify, and learn live coding. Furthermore, Scrawlink is not only a tool for learning, but for sharing the actual code at live performances. Audiences can access the code producing the audio and visuals, and play it from their phones. Developing an affordable and appropriate way of sharing live coding performances with audiences, in a way that supports them in accessing, understanding, modifying and sharing modifications, was another key driver for the design and development of the tool.

The value proposition and the key features of the tool are summarized in the following four requirements.

Requirements

1. **Easy score sharing:** The tool aims to support simple and reliable sharing of live coding scores.
2. **Performance oriented:** Scores are automatically shared as they are performed.
3. **Playable scores:** The tool provides links to live coding scores within working live coding environments that support directly playing them.
4. **Language agnostic:** Scrawlink supports the sharing of scores of different live coding languages.

4. IMPLEMENTATION

Scrawlink is oriented to web-based live coding environments. This facilitates the easy sharing of playable scores (Design requirements 1 and 3), as the user does not have to download or install any additional software to play the scores. It also facilitates the implementation, as developing web tools that can directly be used in a wide variety of web environments is easier than developing specific tools for different languages using different architectures, development environments and graphical user interfaces (GUIs). Moreover, an increasing number of languages are web-based. Nevertheless, future extensions of the tool could support other languages, sacrificing the requirement of having playable scores but enhancing the language agnostic nature of the proposal (Requirement 4).

The implementation of Scrawlink is available online (Ámbar Tenorio-Fornés and Guillaume Pellerin 2025) under a Free Software license and offered as a web app, a browser extension and as an extension of Hydra visuals live coding language. Figure 1 provides a sequence diagram of the tool to illustrate the flow and behaviour of the application and its components. The following sections describe the main components of the architecture and the different implementations.

⁷ Where “todes” is an explicitly gender neutral “all” used to include women, men and gender-diverse people.

⁸ Sync! Festival de Música Electrónica de Carabanchel: <https://sync.encamino.es/>

Sharing scores in URLs

The first version of Scrawlink supports the sharing of Strudel (music) and Hydra (visuals) live coding scores. These live coding languages are often played within their own web-based environments. Moreover, they both implement a key feature: the URL of the web environment includes the running score as a URL parameter (Berners-Lee 1994), and is automatically updated when code changes are executed. Thus, a live coder can copy the URL from a running Hydra or Strudel session to directly share their code in a working environment. Scrawlink provides easy access to that URL in real time through QR codes.

Figure 1: Scrawlink UML Sequence diagram.

Figure 2: Screenshot of a strudel live coding score with Scrawlink extension.

QR Codes

QR Codes are often used for easy sharing and accessing URLs from smartphones (Tiwari 2016). Scrawlink uses them to share links to the scores, updating a QR code displayed in the bottom right corner of the browser when the live coder updates the running code. Figure 2 shows a screenshot of the tool, with a working QR link.

QR codes are generated using the qrcode.js library (Sangmin 2015). However, the URLs are shortened before to provide smaller and easier to read QR codes as detailed in the following subsection.

URL shortener

Live coding scores can be small enough to fit in a readable QR code. For example, there was a trend where live coders shared live coding snippets in twitter, with a 140 characters limit (Martins and Padovani 2023). However, these codes are often longer than what a usable QR can support. To tackle this challenge, Scrawlink architecture relies on an open source URL shortener (xyTom 2023), that assigns small URLs to each score to keep the QRs readable, which is deployed as a Cloudflare web worker.

Timestamping and backlinks

Scrawlink scores not only share the current running code. It is interesting to know which code preceded current status to be able to reproduce and study the performance. This featured is provided in Scrawlink, adding two URL parameters to store this information: a timestamp of when the code change was executed, and a link to the previous score.

Implementations

Scrawlink is provided in three different and complementary implementations, a web container, a web-browser extension and a Hydra extension. These are further described below.

1. *Web container*

First, users can access the tool through the QR code. This implementation offers a web container that embeds the original linked live coding environment with the linked score, and offers the QR sharing functionality without the need to install anything.

2. *Web browser extension*

However, Scrawlink is also provided as a Chrome web-browser extension, available at the Chrome Web Store. When the web container implementation detects that the user has this extension installed, it redirects the user to the corresponding live coding environment.

3. *Hydra extension*

Finally, Scrawlink is available as a standard Hydra extension, and users can include it with a simple click from the extensions' gallery.

Supported languages

In addition to Hydra (visuals) and Strudel (music), Scrawlink supports WebPD, a compiler for the Pure Data audio programming language allowing to run .pd patches in web pages (Piquemal 2024). This easy integration is thanks to the use of URLs parameters for the instrument and its state, as Strudel and Hydra does.

5. EVALUATION

The tool has been evaluated in different performances, showcasing different uses of the tool, and helping to find the limitations and needed improvements. This section describes two workshops and two performances using Scrawlink that aimed to test different applications of the tool. The different nature of these events help to illustrate the practical applications of the tool, and provided valuable insights about the strengths and limitations of the proposal.

Evaluation at live coding workshops

The tool was first introduced at a live coding workshop at Sync festival. During the workshop, participants learned live coding using Strudel. Scrawlink was used in the laptop of the facilitator. Participants understood the tool. However, in this setting it was easier to share code using a chat than using QR codes, as people were coding using their laptops and not their smartphones. A similar experience happened during a presentation at the Live Coders Meetup of VIU 2023 festival (Tenorio-Fornés 2023), where the audience was encouraged to play a 3 minutes piece starting from a previous performance's code. The participants found it easier to share the URLs to their code using a shared collaborative document.

The use of Scrawlink does not seem to be appropriate to share code with participants using their computers during the workshops. However, it might be useful to people seeing the recordings afterwards.

Evaluation at live performances

Short after introducing Scrawlink in a workshop, the tool was used at a live performance at the same festival. This performance helped to test the tool in a live environment. The original version of the tool did not include a URL-shortener, and worked in the lab environment. After observing the difficulties to read long QR codes in real performance environments, with different light and quality of the projections, the URL-shortener was included to reduce the information in the QRs, and therefore making them easier to read. In this performance for a non-specialized audience, participants understood that the QR gave access to the code, but didn't understand that they could play it afterwards, or if changing the code would change the performance's code. The

non-specialized audience showed interest in the tool after it was explained, but did not understand it by just seeing it live. Thus, this first performance helped to validate the proof of concept of the tool in a live environment, and also helped to identify some of its limitations.

A more recent performance for specialized audiences showed that participants could be asked to scan and play the QR codes to produce live coding sounds from their phones (Tenorio Fornés 2024). At the beginning of this performance, the audience could access and play a code to produce birds and insects sounds from their phones. Some participants understood the tool and played different bird sounds from their phones, but others did not see that the QR code changed when the performer evaluated the code. After using Scrawlink for the audio part of the performance, some participants also used it to access the visuals from their phones, showing the interest and understanding of the proposal.

In conclusion, Scrawlink is useful for live coding performances, although participants might need an explanation of how it works. Furthermore, Scrawlink can be used to produce collaborative sessions where different sounds come from different devices. However, some improvements are still needed to better communicate how the application works. For instance, a blink to highlight every update of the QR codes might help to understand that a new code is available to scan.

6. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSIONS

The paper has introduced Scrawlink, a Free Software tool for live sharing of live coding scores. Scrawlink allows not only sharing the score, but also playing, modifying and sharing derivative pieces. It offers reliable access to the performance code, not often fully available by just the sharing of screens. Moreover, the tool is designed with non-technical users in mind, focusing on usability and easy to play the scores.

The tool offers a language agnostic manner to share scores and register live performances. It shares the code in an affordable and culturally appropriate way, as it uses simple links, but more importantly, because it shares live coding in a way that further supports live coding, as the shared piece can be played and modified by the users. Despite supporting different languages, Scrawlink is skewed towards web based languages, and sharing scores of other languages would not support a key feature such as directly playing and modifying the piece.

Scrawlink is fully functional, however it is still in early stages of development. The evaluation of the tools showed different applications and interest of the tool, but also showed some of its current limitations. Additionally, some privacy and security concerns are worth mentioning.

Privacy and Security

One of the risks of code evaluation online is the exposure to malicious software (Yue and Wang 2009). This risk increases if arbitrary code can be injected into the application through the URL. Scrawlink does not mitigate this existing risk in languages such as Hydra or Strudel, and its use can incentivize malicious actors to exploit it.

Regarding privacy, the current implementation of Scrawlink, automatically shares the performed code changes to a single URL shortener service (maintained by Scrawlink). Making other services available, and letting users decide when to share and when not to share the code changes would help with these privacy concerns.

Limitations

Scrawlink functionality is limited to sharing live coding scores. Access to code is a precondition for the Free Software freedoms that Scrawlink aims to support. However, code is not the only important element at a live coding performance, although it is often highly fetishized in live coding (J. Armitage

and Thornham 2021) and other Free Software communities (Rozas et al. 2021). Moreover, the mere sharing of code is often not enough to understand the performances (Collins et al. 2003; Dal Ri and Masu 2022; Cocker 2016). Thus, Scrawlink is just a tool to share a playable snapshot of the live coding scores within a working live coding environment. Its success as a tool to support diversity, accessibility and collaboration depends on the adoption by existing communities within other diverse tools and practices (J. L. Armitage 2018).

Future Work

The testing of the software in different settings for different audiences and purposes shows the interest and applications of the proposal. However, these experiences have also helped to find some needed improvements in the interface, such as highlighting that the QR code changes when the code evaluation happens to add clarity.

The support of other live coding languages is one of the key future developments to improve the proposal. Some languages are straightforward to implement, as they already use URL parameters to share their code and status such as Mercury (Hoogland, n.d.) or P5Live⁹. Some collaborative live coding environments could also use Scrawlink to provide access to the sessions. Environments like Estuary and Flok would also support Scrawlink directly, as the session info is included in the URL. Other web languages would require development efforts to update their URLs as the live coding code changes. The proposal of a standard for this use of URL parameters would facilitate the adoption of Scrawlink in those languages. Standardization would also help to avoid some of the challenges mentioned above, such as using the appropriate software version to play the scores. Furthermore, non web environments could also use Scrawlink to share scores (although they would not be directly playable, they could include links to the live used coding languages along the scores).

The development of a navigation functionality to go back to previous stages of the score, and a session player that executes the code changes with the same intervals as recorded would also be interesting improvements. This information is already present in Scrawlink links. However, it is worth noticing that not all sessions can be reproduced exactly as they were performed, as processes such as feedback are very sensitive to time, and even the performance of the system can affect the results. Moreover, some instructions, such as those using random numbers, are explicitly non-replicable unless the performer uses tricks such as setting the random seed explicitly in the code.

Finally, the development of an archive of live coding scores would be useful as a channel to share and store live coding scores. This archive should be under community governance, and serve the live coding community needs and values.

Live sharing of live coding scores could be a key practice to transform live coding, improving sharing, collaboration and publishing practices. Scrawlink proposes a tool to facilitate this, but the success of the proposal depends on community adoption and stewardship.

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⁹ Available online: <https://teddavis.org/p5live/>

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